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INDEX

Sr. No.	Title of the Paper	Name of Author	Page No.
01.	APPROACH OF HOMEOPATHY IN MANAGEMENT OF NEPHROLITHIASIS	Dr. Ratnaparkhi P. M. Dr. Padmashri Nilesh Samei	01
02.	HOMOEOPATHIC MANAGMENT OF IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA IN CHILDREN: A REVIEW	Dr. Anagha Beedkar Dr. Mahesh Kumar Samrite	06
03.	EFFECTIVENESS OF HOMOEOPATHIC REMEDIES IN TREATING RENAL CALCULI – A CASE DISCUSSION	Dr. Suresh V. Tathe Dr. Satwick Sistu	09
04.	STUDY OF MARKETING FUNCTIONS IN PERISHABLE & NON-PERISHABLE COMMODITIES: CASE OF NANDED & PARBHANI DISTRICT	Abhishek O. Gill Dr. G.P. Mudholkar	14
05.	REVIEW ON SICKLE CELL ANEMIA: A CURRENT SCENARIO FROM DHULIA DISTRICT (M.S.), INDIA	S. S. PATOLE	32
06.	“THE GENERAL ASPECTS OF HISTOMORPHOLOGY OF VIRUSES WITH THEIR HARMFUL AND HARMLESS EFFECTS”	Namrata Rajesh Dhanajkar	38
07.	A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PERSONALITY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF PRIVATE AND GOVERNMENT SECTOR	Dr. Manoj Kumar maurya Gayatri Soni	43
08.	REGIONAL PARTIES IN INDIA- ISSUES AND CHALLENGES	Hamsa Ramakrishna	53
09.	CONTRIBUTION OF BUDDHIST THINKERS FOR THE WORLDSOCIETY: AN INTRODUCTION	Dr. SONAM ZANGPO	60
10.	MULTICULTURALISM IN HARI KUNZRU'S <i>TRANSMISSION</i>	Mr. Mangesh Digambar Panchal	66
11.	ROLE OF WOMEN IN FREEDOM MOVEMENT IN INDIA: STRUGGLE & OPPORTUNITY	Gurpinder Kumar	70
12.	READING THE CHANNEL OF SKILLS	Dr. Chanchal Sharma	76
13.	'EFFECTS AND CHALLENGES OF ONLINE ADVERTISING'	Dharmendra Shakya	79
14.	IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION & YOGA IN DAILY HUMAN LIFE	Dr. Ganesh S. Solunke	81
15.	THE PORTRYAL OF INDIA AS NATION IN CRISIS IN ANANDMATH	Jadhav Jaishree Shivajirao	83

READING THE CHANNEL OF SKILLS

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ABSTRACT:

Bacon in his 'off studies' says 'Reading makes the full man conference ready and writing an exact man'. These lines are the zest and centre figure of all kind of knowledge. All the knowledge is round about it. There is a term Renaissance defined in the history of English literature which means the rebirth or reawakening of classical Greek learning after the negligence. Today we have entered in the new magical technological world. Here it has become a big challenge to maintain balance between old and new technique of reading. Means to say that its a rebirth of skills through the technology platform. Where we are able to enhance our skills easily without any wastage of time through this platform. Through E Library we can read more books which improve our reading skill. In E Library different types of reading material on various subjects is available. Its very true if we read more then we get more. If we follow the chain of listening, reading, writing, and finally speaking then definitely we get success in our different field. The main purpose of the paper is how to improve and represent the skills through the new technology. Books are our best friends which shows light in our life. Bacon is quiet right when he says, 'Studies serve for delight, for ornament and for ability.' Its an aroma in our life. Where we can prove our ability. And technology pour life in this chain.

Key words: Reading, Perfect, Skills, Communication.

PAPER :

In this materialistic world nobody is our best friend but there is no doubt to say that in fact books are our best friends. These life skills fills new energy in our life. All these skills are related to our brain. Brain which works in our body like computer. It react when it receives the message from body. With the help of brain man can think and experience, emotions, it is the root of human intelligence. These skills which improves our personality are related to our brain. when we listen then brain starts its work and response. Then finally man speaks. Through them we can learn humanistic attitudes. Now -a- days technology is playing a very important part which enrich our skills. Technology is just like a new magical gate through it we can improve our these all skills along with personal and professional relations to. Bacon says, in 'Off Studies' 'Reading makes a full man, writing an exact man, conference a ready man.' so through these lines we are able to improve our personality and technology help in this. Its a technology where we are able to get different books on various topics in E Library. The most significant event which marks the cause the Renaissance in England in the Europeopion invention of printing from movable trap. The hand crafted manuscript was replaced by the mass produced book. And from there the reading public appeared. Renaissance means the knowledge from dark age to present. William Caxton (c.1422-c.1491) an English merchant, diplomat, and a writer has brought printing press in this world in 1476. From there the book and reading culture come in our life. In the connection of this running chain reading, listening, writing and finally speaking skills are interconnected. Not only reading but also listening is also a very important aspect. It may be defined as the perception or actual understanding which has to be communicated. Perception and understanding differs from person to person. Listening is not an easy

process. Most of the person they never listen seriously, or carefully. Without listening you can't take the right message. Reading books is a very important part of our life, they are our best friends. During middle age people learned there lesson and then pass it through mouth to moth .But after Caxton printing press it has become very easy to spread lessons with the help of books. According to Floyd J. James, 'less listing capacity is a main source or origin of the problems related with the work at every level. As Bacon says 'reading makes the man perfect so yes it is true .Through reading we get knowledge of different areas .But for this you have to be a good listener.with the help of writing man will become a good accurate and finally he will become a perfect man . Then he will speak also. So its a wonderfully chain Listening,reading, writing and conference. In the connection of listening it has become a very important aspect related to other skills. For this skills we have to follow some tools these are as follows

- 1.Stop talking while listing.
- 2.Avoid chit chat .
- 3.Give liberty to speaker.
- 4.Don't take any self decision .

After listening ask question. Reading is based on a good reader. When the reader read something then thoughts ,facts ,meaning and information he will get. Reading is a process and you will become a good learner. To improve the reading your vocabulary must be strong .There are 3 types of reading.

- 1.Pre Reading
- 2.while reading
- 3.post Reading .

For 1st pre reading you have to understand the text. In while reading it encourage the thinking of a student. In post reading its check that you are right. Its include some stage like seek feedback. You have to explain the meaning, purpose of your reading .To improve reading skills then don't bound yourself with one book. Reading is an active process so improve your critical thinking and try to know about it more. Bacon says in 'Off Studies 'Read not to contradict and confute; nor to believe and take for granted'.Again he says,'Some books are to be tasted others to be swallowed, and some few to be chewed and digisted.'According to this the process of reading through which sometimes we read

- 1.only the heading or the title.
- 2.Sometime inside the para.
- 3.Sometime fully.

So overall these are just based on your habit how you take it. There are so many types of reading : 1.Skimming ...In such type of reading we just read the zest or just to know the main idea. With the help of this reader is able to improve his knowledge.

- 2.Scanning..... Readers in such type of reading scuttles across sentences wants to know the particular piece of information.
3. Intensive reading ..This type of reading the reader has to know everything and understand the meaning also .In it reader has to give time. He has to take help from dictionary also. so that he will be able to know the meaning.
- 4.Extensive ...In this type reader has to emphasison fluency and less on accuracy .Its only for pleasure. Where you just read only to passyour time. For example magazine, jokes, news paper etc.

But its taking differ from person to person .Listening is not a simple process most of the person they are unable to listen properly or carefully without listening it is not possible to pass or take the masses effectively to other .Listening and reading both of are just like a two side of a one coin ,they are interconnected. when books were not there in the middle ages of people they learnt their lesson but when books come in our lives than it has become easier for us to read it and listen it .Listening , reading ,writing and conference in this process listening is a very important. It improve your critical thinking and try to know more about the situation. It begins in of studies,in this way Bacon says,read not to contradict ,nor to believe and take for granted. He also says again that some books are to be tasted. IN other words reading is in the same way the process in which some time we read only the heading of the title sometime inside the para sometime fully. In the connection of short types of reading skimming is Just to know the main Idea. scanning reading scattered across sentences to get particular piece of information intensive reading time confused consuming reading has to read and understand the meaning. The dictionary you have to use in extensive reading their reader has to emphasize on fluency and lesser accuracy. It's only for the pleasure or the enjoyment that's it. Listening, reading and writing a written documentits different thing .Here it become a permanent record. Other can review it in the masses so this record from time to time maintain written recordfor future and that's why its a very important part. The skill can be divided into four parts planning first draught amendment and editing when we make a plan to write something then there should be a selection of thought the next step include connectivity. Thoughts into words and sentences in a systematic order in the last section .A man write and then the do editing. We have to add few necessary section. we have to use simple words appropriate subjects that should be selected.The convert the masses avoid unnecessary words and sentences if these steps we use then we will present a very dynamic performance .Before wrap up the topic it should be clear to say that reading is a channel of skills in its connection listening writing then speaking are all if we blended carefully in a interconnected way then you can represent yourself any where. Nobody is complete in itself. So you have to follow all these rules and then you will become a perfect man. During this Era which has become a digital world where we have to be able and to enhance our self thought the new technology. In this untouched new world of education means online work, the communication is playing a very important role. In which we have to prepare ourselves sound in the field of listening reading and writing and then pass a message to the words in the form of sentences.In the e-Learning world now we have easily enter into the world of books through the e-library are there. In a small Canvas we have to get so many books on different topics.

It's a fact more we read more we learn now we have become a digital mechanical person.If somebody wants to improve his skill then he has to take help from the new technology and then get perfection in his area easily. It work like an Aroma in our life.

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